

Bridging Education Equality for Underprivileged Youths Through Spatial Designs in Public Libraries in Shanghai

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ABSTRACT

Public libraries are a shared space where people of different age, gender, and income level interact with one another to bridge differences with their common goal of learning. In an age where online information is readily accessible, library attendees increasingly value the unique physical space that libraries offer which is not present in their homes. This is especially true for underprivileged youths who view public libraries as a second home. This research surveyed 109 underprivileged and privileged youths in order to compare their needs in a library's spatial designs with the final goal of recommending spatial designs features public libraries could include. Interviews with eight renowned libraries internationally, and the researcher's observations at the Shanghai Pudong Library are also included to add additional insights. While seating space is a top consideration for both groups, the results show that underprivileged youths value the basic functions of a library while the privileged desire a more aesthetic value. This research also suggests that future research could dive into improving architectural structures of public libraries to be more youth-focused.

Keywords: *Education equality, underprivileged youths, public libraries, spatial designs, China*

1. INTRODUCTION

Since the 2020 COVID-19 pandemic causing a global shutdown, public library attendance has decreased. Notably, up to 90% of book borrowing numbers decreased for the majority of the British libraries (McMenemy et al., 2022). Additionally, funding still decreased for many public libraries (Jaeger et al., 2013). This halts the opportunity to learn for underprivileged communities, specifically youths, despite the library's past efforts. Approximately 14 million

eleven to eighteen year olds are on their own after school (Young Adult Library Services Association, 2012). Considering how juvenile crime rates peak in these after school hours, public libraries are the vital safe space for youths (Nolin et al., 2015). Libraries are a shared public space, an “extension” of the home and office. Public libraries are seen as crucial to improving a communal bond for children in Bangalore’s slums as it becomes a social space (Pyati & Kamal, 2012). Additionally, as public libraries are no longer the sole provider of internet access, their new purpose must be one that cannot be found in everyone’s home—a library experience with their space. Library design is an essential element proven by successful examples around the globe (Nicholson, 2017). Boston Public Library saw a 45% increase in attendance since a simple change in its seating (Knox, 2022).

This research paper explores the relationship between the needs of underprivileged youths in Shanghai and how spatial designs in libraries can support their learning. This essay strives to fill the research gap by drawing on international case studies of public libraries that pioneered their spatial designs to propose a recommendation for other libraries that wish to increase the library usage by underprivileged youths.

2. METHODOLOGY

2.1 Aim of the study

The main purpose of the study is to determine the benefits of spatial designs on underprivileged youths, while the specific objectives are to:

1. Identify if there are any challenges at home for underprivileged youths living in Shanghai that prevent them from learning effectively.
2. Summarize underprivileged youths' desirable spatial features in Shanghai public libraries that can address the challenges they face at home, therefore provide a positive learning environment.
3. Assess potential spatial improvements that Shanghai public libraries could implement by drawing from successful global examples to better serve underprivileged youths.

2.2 Research Design

Cross-sectional research was employed in this study, utilizing three types of observational methods: surveys, interviews, and observations. The survey design incorporated independent variables related to spatial design factors that both underprivileged and privileged youths value in libraries, as well as the challenges they face at home and in library settings. These factors were identified by the researcher based on common challenges related to both environments.

The researcher investigated the extent to which underprivileged and privileged youths encountered challenges in working comfortably at home, influenced by factors such as lack of privacy, inadequate air conditioning, limited access to books, slow or nonexistent internet access, insufficient space, poor lighting, safety concerns, high noise levels, and family responsibilities. Additionally, the researcher examined which spatial factors in libraries were most valued by these youths, offering options such as window views, privacy, air conditioning, spaciousness, adequate lighting, and controlled noise levels. The study also assessed the spatial factors that hindered library usage among underprivileged and privileged youths, including lack of window views, insufficient privacy, inadequate air conditioning, limited seating, poor lighting, and overcrowding.

The dependent variables were the perceptions of underprivileged and privileged youths regarding these factors, measured using rating scales. For the question addressing which factor posed the greatest challenge, the scales of “Most Challenging,” “Less Challenging,” and “Not Challenging” were utilized. To determine the spatial factor that underprivileged youths valued most, scales of “Most Valuable,” “Somewhat Valuable,” and “Little or Not Valuable” were applied. For assessing the spatial factors that prevent increased library usage, scales of “Greatly Affect,” “Somewhat Affect,” and “Not At All Affect” were employed. These scales facilitated quantification of each factor through numerical ratings for comparative analysis.

Surveys were selected as the primary observational method for both underprivileged and privileged youths. Underprivileged youths represented a significant demographic within public libraries, relying on these spaces for learning and safety. The results from privileged youths served as a comparative measure to better understand the needs of their underprivileged counterparts. Consequently, the perceptions and experiences of youths were effectively captured through surveys, which can provide valuable insights for creating more inclusive and supportive library environments.

The research also included interviews with librarians from libraries worldwide. Email interviews were chosen to accommodate time zone differences and language barriers. These interviews were particularly relevant as the libraries involved are globally recognized for their spatial designs that cater to underprivileged populations. Through these discussions, the research gained personal and professional insights from librarians who regularly engage with these library environments.

Additionally, the researcher's personal observations at the Shanghai Library were incorporated as an observational method, allowing for the collection of data during specific time periods that was not documented on the official library website.

2.3 Hypotheses

Hypothesis 1: Underprivileged youths face more challenges at home that prevent them from learning efficiently compared to privileged youths.

Hypothesis 2: Underprivileged youths utilize the seating area more compared to privileged youths.

Hypothesis 3: Underprivileged youths are more sensitive to undesirable spatial factors in libraries compared to privileged youths, which may discourage them from visiting libraries.

2.4 Consent and Ethical Considerations

All ethical considerations were followed for the current study. Surveys were collected anonymously, participants were informed that the survey was for research-purpose only, and their personal information would not be disclosed to a third party. Verbal consent from participants was obtained before the survey was distributed. No identifiers such as names or pictures were disclosed in the paper or while conducting the study. Emails sent to international librarians clearly stated the purpose. If no initial response was received, no further contact was made to avoid soliciting. All information shared in this article was permitted by the librarians, it involves no confidential or private data.

2.5 Sample

The survey participants comprised a total of 109 responses. Among these, 11% were aged 10-14, 23.85% were aged 15-18, and 37.61% were aged 18-24. The study adopted the United Nations' 2013 definition of youth, which includes individuals aged 15 to 24 (United Nations,

2013). Additionally, individuals aged 10 to 15 were included, as books read by this group are often found in the same young adult section of libraries. 60% (n=65) of the participants met at least three criteria for being underprivileged, while 40% (n=44) did not meet any of these criteria and were classified as privileged. The criteria included household income, number of siblings, family status, parents' education level, safety after school, and metropolitan status. Purposive sampling was conducted through two channels. The researcher first identified youths at the Shanghai Pudong Library through observation and preliminary questions before inviting them to complete the survey. Additionally, digital surveys were distributed to individuals and groups of students from public non-selective middle and high schools, which have a higher proportion of lower-income students. This approach was designed to maximize the participation of underprivileged youth. The insights of 109 survey participants were sufficient to help identify general trends in the needs of underprivileged versus privileged youth.

The researcher also conducted email interviews with librarians from eight renowned international libraries: this includes the Seattle Public Library, National Library of New Zealand, Auckland Council Library, British Library, National Library of Israel, State Library of Victoria, Royal Danish Library, and Bibliotheca Alexandrina. These libraries were chosen for their global reputation and advanced spatial design features, representing four different continents. A total of 27 emails were exchanged. Select excerpts from these exchanges can be found in the appendix. The insights from these libraries provide valuable perspectives on successful spatial design strategies used worldwide.

2.6 Scales used/tools used/instruments used

The survey software Microsoft Forms was utilized for data collection. The survey comprised 23 questions, including 12 multiple-choice questions, 3 ordinal scale questions, 7 open-ended questions, and one numerical rating scale question. Multiple-choice questions were employed to gather demographic information, enabling the determination of whether participants were underprivileged. Ordinal scale questions allowed respondents to assess various factors based on a scale of three, ranking them from most to least influential. Open-ended questions provided participants the opportunity to offer additional recommendations not included in the answer choices. Finally, a numerical rating scale question was included at the end of the survey to elicit an overall rating from 1 to 10.

For the email interviews with librarians from international libraries, the initial round consisted of open-ended questions focused on spatial designs and the utilization of these spaces by underprivileged youth. The initial email was distributed to libraries in 25 countries, ensuring inclusivity by reaching out to at least two libraries from each of the seven continents. Eight libraries responded, and follow-up emails containing additional open-ended questions were subsequently sent. The responses incorporated librarians' personal insights, along with official photos, videos, and internal documents.

Qualitative observational methods were employed to count the number of youths and total users of specific spatial features in the Shanghai Pudong Library over a designated two-week period. This approach aimed to estimate the proportions of youths and identify the most effective spatial designs within the library.

2.7 Data Collection Procedure

Data from the surveys was collected through online distribution and exposure at the Shanghai Pudong Library. Surveys were administered at 12:00 p.m. on August 25, 2024, as this time was identified as having the highest observed foot traffic on the ground floor when attendees typically leave for lunch. Data collection continued on the same dates, allowing participants sufficient time to complete the survey. When a youth was spotted by the researcher on the ground floor, a verbal confirmation of their general age was obtained to ensure they qualified as youths. The researcher then requested their participation in the survey, assuring them of confidentiality. A poster featuring the survey QR code was subsequently provided to the participant for completion at their convenience.

The researcher also recorded personal observations of space usage within the Shanghai Library, detailed in a Word document complemented by photographs. Observations were conducted at 19:00 on weekends over two consecutive weeks: August 24–25 and August 31–September 1, 2024. The researcher traversed the floors with study spaces to count the number of youths and total attendees during specific time periods. The second round of observations focused on counting attendees and youths in three specific spatial features of the Shanghai Pudong Library: the shelves, special study tables, and staircase seating. Youths were identified based on their use of middle school, high school, and university textbooks.

Interviews were conducted via email throughout August 2024. Requests for email interviews were sent to various library institutions worldwide using the official email addresses listed on

the libraries’ websites. If librarians agreed to share information, the researcher responded within a day with follow-up questions. Librarians were encouraged to attach photos and additional observations to enhance the understanding of personal library experiences globally. Up to four exchanges occurred before concluding each interview. By the end of August 2024, all data was collected for analysis.

3. RESULTS

3.1 Challenges Youth Face At Home

Figure 1: How Much Each Factor Challenge Underprivileged Youths At Home From Working Comfortably

Figure 2: How Much Each Factor Challenge Privileged Teens At Home From Working Comfortably

The top three factors for underprivileged youths in sequence are family duties, high noise level, and slow or no internet access (Figure 1). The top three challenges for privileged youths in sequence are high noise level, family duties, and insufficient space (Figure 2). Even though family duties are a common factor, it is more of a challenge for underprivileged youths. Underprivileged youths are also more concerned about internet access. Underprivileged youths select more factors as “Most Challenging” compared to privileged youths.

3.2 Spatial Factors Youth Value The Most In A Library

Figure 3: The Spatial Factors Underprivileged Teens Value The Most In A Library

Figure 4: The Spatial Factors Privileged Teens Value The Most In A Library

The top three factors underprivileged youths the most are spacious rooms, sufficient lighting and controlled noise level (Figure 3). The top three factors privileged youths the most are controlled noise level, spacious room, and privacy (Figure 4). Underprivileged youths value lighting and a spacious room more than privileged youths. In general, privileged youths value spatial design more than underprivileged youths.

3.3 Undesirable Spatial Factors That Prevents Youth From Using The Library More

Figure 5: Spatial Factors That Prevents Underprivileged Teens From using The Library More

Figure 6: Spatial Factors That Prevents Privileged Teens From using The Library More

The top three spatial factors that prevent underprivileged youths from using the library more ranks as lack of air conditioning, lack of seating space, and insufficient lighting (Figure 5). The top three spatial factors that prevent privileged youths from using the library more ranks as lack of seating space, lack of privacy, and the library being crowded and busy (Figure 6). Even though the lack of seating space is a shared concern, privileged youths feel affected by it more. Similar to previous trends, privileged youths value their privacy more especially when the library is crowded and busy. On the other hand, underprivileged youths feel concerned about the lighting, also supported by the previous data. One unpredicted factor of concern for underprivileged youths is air conditioning.

3.4 Successful Library Designs Internationally: Lighting

As adequate lighting is a key aspect of spatial design valued by underprivileged youths, we can draw on successful examples from renowned libraries worldwide.

The Bibliotheca Alexandrina uses glass ceilings and pillars in the largest circular diaphragm wall in the world. The tilted glass roof is to provide a shade against the south desert Sun while showing a view of the Mediterranean waters surrounding the building (Zahran & Muhsin, 2007, pp.102). The reading room rests under this ceiling to get the best lighting. The warm colors, lighting, and customized furniture were designed specifically to create a

welcoming and comfortable space. Specific designs include wooden floors, rust colored carpets, and metal web to make the lighting softer (Fundación Internacional De Síntesis Arquitectónica & Aga Khan Trust for Culture, 1999, pp.41).

From the researcher's observations in the Shanghai East Library, customized table lamps attached as a rod across a table were used to provide sufficient illumination for all seated. For the Shanghai Pudong Library, three lamps are found on every table for six. Additionally, tall glass ceilings are used for natural lighting. Study desks are placed directly next to the window walls. Through conversations with librarians, the researcher learned that the seats right next to windows are the most popular because of the view and lighting. Similarly, The National Library of Israel does the same by integrating glass in the vitrines of reading spaces, with the aim to create a space that is welcoming to all ages, cultures, and income levels (Herzog & de Meuron, 2023). For the Te Manawa Library which won the 2020 Auckland Architecture awards, the designers also placed emphasis on glass to foster a sense of connection (New Zealand Institute of Architects, 2020) (Archipro, 2019). In the Seattle Public Library, large glass windows are utilized to create a sense of openness and natural lighting (Seattle Public Library, 2014). According to the architect Joshua Prince-Ramus, the angled glass structure is to maximize the water and street view. The diamond glass grid is to specifically let in natural winter and block out strong summer rays (Prince-Ramus, 2006).

3.5 Successful Library Designs Internationally: Privacy

In the open-ended survey, the majority of 9 privileged youths expressed a desire for libraries to enhance privacy for attendees, emphasizing the importance of a quiet environment. Privacy is also a significant factor valued by underprivileged youths in library settings, and examples can be drawn from various libraries.

At the Bibliotheca Alexandrina, the Reading Hall features individual desks for computer users, which fosters a sense of comfort and privacy (Serageldin, 2006, pp. 40). Similarly, the Shanghai Pudong Library's large stepped reading halls are designed to provide privacy and a sense of spaciousness (Zahran & Muhsin, 2007, pp. 60). Additionally, the Shanghai Pudong Library includes individual booths for private phone calls.

The Shanghai East Library enhances privacy by using translucent glass to separate shared tables while maintaining an open atmosphere. In the Royal Danish Library, blue separation boards serve a similar purpose (Royal Danish Library, 2023). Both the Shanghai East Library

and the Royal Danish Library feature specialized tables, such as elevated tables, to create unique private spaces (Royal Danish Library, 2023).

3.6 Successful Library Designs Internationally: Seating

Based on the survey results, a substantial number of underprivileged youths recommended increasing seating in reading areas. This aligns with the researcher's conversations with library staff at the Shanghai Pudong Library, where it was noted that seats often become scarce and that these study spaces are among the most utilized areas in the library. The researcher observed a significantly higher number of people using the seating area for studying compared to those browsing the bookshelves. Insights can be drawn from internationally renowned libraries regarding seating arrangements.

For instance, similar to how the Shanghai East Library has added couches facing window walls, the Royal Danish Library mitigates the sense of claustrophobia in study areas by positioning tables in front of an expansive two-floor space. Additionally, the library offers a variety of chair and couch designs to accommodate diverse needs, ranging from studying to relaxation (Royal Danish Library, 2023). The Shanghai Pudong Library also features customized seating, including slanted tables specifically designed for newspaper reading, to provide additional seating options. However, in the researcher's observations, these tables are used more for relaxation and work than for their intended purpose.

The La Trobe Reading Room, known as The Dome, is a notable feature of the State Library of Victoria (Hogan, 2024). Harriet Edquist, a Professor of Architectural History at RMIT, described the spacious white interior of The Dome as a "clearing house of thought," fostering a comfortable environment for study (Grant, 2023).

The architect of the Seattle Public Library envisioned it as a public space accessible to individuals of all income levels. Seats in the Teen Center are specifically reserved for youth. The librarian at the Seattle Public Library highlighted the variety of seating available, which includes counter-height tables, group tables, couches, and round tables suitable for various purposes (Seattle Public Library, 2014).

The Bibliotheca Alexandrina, completed in 2002, was designed with the underprivileged community in mind, particularly in light of Egypt's booming population. The library aimed for a design that is "large in size but always human in scale" while constructing the largest

reading room in the world, featuring 78 reader desks and a total of 2,000 seats (Zahran & Muhsin, 2007, pp. 103 & 256; Serageldin, 2006, pp. 15). The Young People's Library is specifically directed toward youth, providing them with their own dedicated study space (Serageldin, 2006, pp. 41).

3.7 Successful Library Designs Internationally: Greenery

Privileged youths recommended increasing greenery in public libraries in response to open-ended questions. The Royal Danish Library emphasizes the incorporation of greenery, featuring an indoor garden and a vertical garden wall. This wall, referred to as “the green heart of the library,” is designed to create a tranquil environment, allowing the garden and the sound of water to encourage mindfulness and facilitate a slower pace for visitors. A diverse selection of plants with varying shades of green has been carefully chosen (Royal Danish Library, 2023). Similarly, the Shanghai Pudong Library includes indoor ceiling gardens, while greenery also adorns the steep staircase connecting two floors in the regular seating areas. However, conversations with librarians revealed that this space is not as popular as the primary seating area.

At the Te Manawa Library, the designers created a tinted glass balcony that offers a view of the surrounding outdoor greenery (Archipro, 2019). In the National Library of Israel, glass is employed to showcase the native garden and landscape. The use of wooden frames in the vitrines adds a natural touch, enhancing a sense of calm and welcoming for attendees.

4. DISCUSSION

Underprivileged youths place greater value on the basic principles of a library, such as access to seating, adequate lighting, and air conditioning. These are essential elements that they may lack at home, leading them to rely more heavily on school and district libraries. In contrast, the survey indicates that privileged youths are primarily concerned with privacy. Their recommendations extend beyond basic library functions, including requests for vending machines and an increase in greenery and windows, reflecting a focus on the aesthetic value of the library. This suggests that privileged youths have higher expectations for public spaces than for their home environments. Their engagement with viral libraries online, which emphasize aesthetics rather than merely functional services, reinforces this notion.

Nevertheless, both groups expressed concerns regarding a lack of seating, as observed when youths studying primarily utilized regular seating areas.

Hypothesis 1 posited that underprivileged youths face greater challenges at home, a claim supported by findings indicating they are more affected by family responsibilities and other factors. This may be attributed to the tendency for both parents in underprivileged families to work, resulting in increased responsibilities for the youths, such as caring for siblings. Hypothesis 2 suggested that underprivileged youths utilize seating areas more frequently; however, this hypothesis is challenged by the finding that both privileged and underprivileged youths highly value seating space, as their primary use of the library is for studying. Privileged youths place a greater emphasis on privacy, possibly because underprivileged youths are accustomed to more crowded home environments. Hypothesis 3 predicted that underprivileged youths are more sensitive to undesirable spatial factors in libraries, but this is challenged by statistics showing that privileged youths express greater concern regarding spatial designs. This may stem from their expectations for an enhanced experience that exceeds what they have at home, while underprivileged youths, lacking such spaces, have lower expectations.

These findings suggest that libraries located in neighborhoods with significant underprivileged populations should prioritize resources to maximize the provision of basic library functions. This is particularly relevant as underprivileged youths tend to frequent their nearest neighborhood library, while privileged youths often visit larger, more renowned facilities. Once these fundamental needs are met, libraries could enhance their offerings of greenery and privacy to attract more privileged youths.

Regarding lighting, underprivileged youths require sufficient illumination at each seating area. It is recommended that lamps be provided to ensure each seat has adequate lighting, with at least one lamp for every two users. This could be complemented by window walls to maximize natural light, with seating placed adjacent to these windows. Interviews also revealed a common theme of creating a sense of natural light and openness through the use of window walls, glass ceilings, and high ceilings.

Libraries with high foot traffic must increase the number of study seats available for underprivileged youths, which could consist of basic chairs and desks. Couches should also be included to provide a place for underprivileged youths to rest. Recommendations include

establishing a dedicated youth center with reserved seating, ensuring that underprivileged youths who lack a proper study environment at home always have a space in the library. Study areas should ideally be situated in the most spacious sections of the library, featuring tall ceilings to alleviate feelings of claustrophobia. Additionally, public couches near study areas can serve as both a resting place and an extra seating option to accommodate growing demand. As evidenced by international libraries, tables typically range from individual setups to those accommodating a maximum of six users.

Underprivileged youths also require privacy. Translucent boards can be used to separate seats at shared tables, creating individual study spaces without inducing a sense of claustrophobia. Some tables could be designated for individual use to enhance privacy, and these should be strategically placed to avoid close proximity to other tables. Incorporating stairs into seating areas can also provide additional space for youths while enhancing privacy.

Integrating greenery into libraries can benefit underprivileged youths. This could involve constructing garden spaces or walls of plants, or placing potted plants throughout the library to improve the welcoming atmosphere. Windows should offer views of green landscapes outside, as finding a scenic sitting spot is essential for enhancing comfort and overall experience. Such views are particularly valuable for underprivileged populations, as they may be unavailable in their home environments. By incorporating nature into the library design, the aim is to create a soothing environment that distinguishes libraries from other public facilities in the city.

This research addressed the gap in understanding the spatial design of public libraries in Shanghai. While previous studies have discussed internet access and public libraries, few have focused on the contemporary context in which technology is widely accessible and libraries are no longer the sole providers of internet services. Additionally, earlier research did not offer a comprehensive organization of various spatial design ideas from international libraries. Building on prior studies that highlight the importance of spatial design and internal resources from librarians, this research expanded the understanding of the modern relationship between underprivileged youths and library design. Thus, the findings of this research could serve as valuable recommendations for libraries considering upgrades to meet the current needs of underprivileged youths.

5. CONCLUSION

The primary objective of this research was to understand how spatial design impacts the library usage of underprivileged youths. The study offered new insights into the differing needs of underprivileged youths, who prioritize fulfilling basic library requirements, while privileged youths tend to focus on aspects related to comfort and aesthetics. This discovery raised additional questions about how libraries can be architecturally modified to meet the evolving demands of underprivileged youths.

Although underprivileged and privileged youths share many commonalities in their library needs, the specific requirements of underprivileged youths warrant greater attention. Given that their needs center around fundamental library functions, addressing these needs could enable libraries to subsequently expand their services to benefit all youths.

The main findings of this research emphasized the significance of lighting, seating space, privacy, and greenery for underprivileged youths. To better serve this demographic, libraries should concentrate on enhancing designs related to these four features. This research has provided specific recommendations for improvement. Future studies could explore architectural designs of libraries to better accommodate the diverse needs of underprivileged youths.

6. LIMITATIONS

The researcher's interviews included a diverse representation of libraries from around the world, encompassing all continents. This diversity highlights the strength of the current study. When collecting data from surveys at Shanghai Pudong Library, challenges arose due to refusals from potential participants. Consequently, the researcher expanded the participant pool by distributing the survey to attendees at various libraries in Shanghai. However, given the focus on a single region, this research may not fully represent the broader population.

The study also compared the needs of underprivileged and privileged youths to gain a comprehensive understanding of the entire youth demographics. Future research should focus on quantitative and empirical studies aimed at identifying optimal spatial designs for learning and updating the physical layouts of public libraries to better meet the evolving needs of underprivileged youths.

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Appendix:

Shanghai library East

Shanghai Library East (Researcher's Own Photo).

Shanghai Pudong Library

Seating Area On Steps (Researcher's Own Photo).

Indoor Ceiling Garden (Researcher's Own Photo).

Specialized Seating at the Shanghai Pudong Library (Researcher's Own Photo).

Seating Area of the Shanghai Pudong Library (Researcher's Own Photo).

Te Manawa Library

Glass Exterior of the Te Manawa Library (Archipro, 2019).

Royal Danish Library

Separating Boards (Royal Danish Library, 2023).

Seating Design (Royal Danish Library, 2023).

Elevated Tables (Royal Danish Library, 2023).

Different Seatings (Royal Danish Library, 2023).

Indoor Garden (Royal Danish Library, 2023)

Planning Map Indoor Garden (Royal Danish Library, 2023).

Wall of Greenery (Royal Danish Library, 2023).

State Library of Victoria

Layout Plan of The Reading Room In The Dome (Grant, 2023)

Bibliotheca Alexandrina

Seating Area of The Reading Hall (Serageldin, 2006)

Seating Area of The Bibliotheca Alexandrina (Serageldin, 2006)

Design Model of The Bibliotheca Alexandrina (Serageldin, 2006)

Seattle Public Library

Seatings In the Teen Center (Photo provided by Librarian, 2024)